

SHORT NOTES

Tetrahalo Complexes of Zinc and Mercury

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The stereochemistry, expected from ligand field theory, for complexes of metals belonging to the first transition series has been listed by Gillespie and Nyholm¹. Since d^0 , d^5 , and d^{10} configurations represent spherically symmetrical non-bonding shells being empty, half full, and full respectively, these are expected to cause the least perturbation to the preferred stereochemistry. The following cations of transition metals have an effective d^{10} configuration: Ni^0 , Cu^{+} , Zn^{2+} , Pd^0 , Ag^{+} , Cd^{2+} , Pt^0 , Au^{+} , Hg^{2+} . The atom Ni^0 has the configuration $3s^2 3p^6 3d^8 4s^2$. The tetrahedral sp^3 hybrid bonds are formed as a result of the degeneration of the $4s$ electrons to the $3d$ level in the case of nickel tetracarbonyl, $Ni^0(CO)_4$. Similar situation is found in $[Cu(CN)_4]^{3-}$ and $[Zn(CN)_4]^{2-}$ ions, which are tetrahedral. Several other complexes have also been reported in the literature². Some more four-co-ordinated halo-complexes of divalent zinc and divalent mercury have been studied and reported in this communication. All these compounds are diamagnetic in solid form, indicating tetrahedral configuration for the $[MX_4]^{2-}$ ion, involving the use of sp^3 hybrid orbitals for bonding. Recently Gill *et al.*³, reported a similar compound $[Ph_3 Me-As]_2 ZnCl_4$, which has properties expected for a four-covalent tetrahedral anion. The tetraiodo-zinc compound is unstable even in the solid state and the relative stabilities of the tetrachloro- and the tetraiodo-zinc compounds are in agreement with the empirical classification listed by Chatt *et al.*⁴.

Procedure.—Some amount of the metal halide, MX_2 (where M is zinc and mercury and X is chloride, bromide or iodide), dissolved in ethanol, was treated with an ethanolic solution of an appropriate amount of quaternary ammonium halide. The separated crystalline compounds were filtered, washed with ethanol, followed by ether, and dried *in vacuo*. The metal and the halogen contents in the dried compounds were estimated to characterise them. Conductance measurements were carried out in water medium using Toshniwal conductivity bridge Type CL 01.02 and all the compounds were found to be 2:1 electrolytes. The analytical data, melting points, and magnetic susceptibility measurements are recorded in Table I

1. *Quart. Rev.*, 1957, 11, 360.
2. Block, "The Chemistry of Co-ordination Compounds", 1956, p. 373.
3. *Quart Rev.*, 1958, 12, 274.
4. *Nature*, 1958, 192, 108.

TABLE I

Compounds	Formula.	% Metal.		% Halogen.		M.P.	$\chi_g \times 10^{-6}$ at 33°.
		found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.		
1. Bis-tetramethylammonium tetrachlorozinc (II)	$[(CH_3)_4N]_2ZnCl_4$	18.8	18.4	39.6	39.9	256°	-0.548
2. Bis-tetramethylammonium tetrabromozinc (II)	$[(CH_3)_4N]_2ZnBr_4$	12.4	12.2	60.2	59.9	> 200°	Diamagnetic
3. Bis-phenyltrimethylammonium tetraiodozinc (II)	$[C_6H_5(CH_3)_3N]_2ZnI_4$	7.2	7.6	59.2	60.1	Decomposes on exposure to atmosphere.	
4. Bis-tetramethylammonium tetrachloromercury (II)	$[(CH_3)_4N]_2HgCl_4$	40.9	41.3	28.0	28.6	284°	-0.313
5. Bis-tetramethylammonium tetrabromomercury (II)	$[(CH_3)_4N]_2HgBr_4$	30.2	30.0	47.1	47.8	245°	-0.309
6. Bis-phenyltrimethylammonium tetraiodomercury (II)	$[C_6H_5(CH_3)_3N]_2HgI_4$	20.3	20.4	51.5	51.7	186°	-0.382

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